

**GEOMARKETING AND REMOTE SENSING FOR MARKETING
AND HOUSING PROPERTIES DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AT
NORTHERN RIYADH**

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ABSTRACT

Determination of market size is a critical factor for the success of any company or business activity. This paper presents a study to provide a clear vision using remote sensing for Geomarketing purposes and industry, in order to estimate market size in the study area based on spatial data. Satellite images, Spot 6, with a 1.5 m resolution, will be used with two different dates during the year 2016, to determine the growth in the housing sector with building types and construction levels in the micro-geographic area of Northern Riyadh, in order to identify the expected need for products of each district and the approximate time required for installation. By using remote sensing data for Geomarketing, strategies for marketing, planning and housing development could be set up.

Science is a critical factor in development and planning in order to serve society and the economy; many science fields have many applications like agriculture with its using in environment and economy, geology with its using in economy and hydrogeology. Last but not least remote sensing with the different applications in Agriculture, Geology, Urban area planning, and business.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Studying Area

Riyadh city the capital of the Saudi Kingdom located at the middle of the country at the intersection of the transportation network, this city was significantly developed by 25 % between 2005 and 2016 (Figure 1.1).

It is extended towards the Northern direction more than to the other directions due to natural obstacles or industrial cities. The studying area (i.e., 240 sq. km) located in the northern part of the town in which recently an essential urban growth and human activities based. Figure (1.1) shows the boundaries of the city in 2005 with yellow color while the blue boundaries at 2018, it shows how the town stretched and expanded

In general, Riyadh is about 30% of the Kingdom population and is increasing horizontally because of the people's here like to live in separate buildings and have privacy.

Figure 1.1 The Growth in Riyadh City Since 2005

According to the 2013 census (Authority of statics) on Riyadh City:

- The population was 5.7 million
- population growth rate of 4% per year
- Number of housing 960000 units
- Number Schools was 3060
- Number of hospitals bed was 14137 beds
- The age group for Saudis under 14 years was 30%
- The age group for Saudis between 15-60 years was 60%
- The average number of the family was 5.97.
- Riyadh city area approximately 1400 sq. km

Figure 1.2. The Study Area at Northern Riyadh City

1.2. Problem Statement

The non-use of spatial information associated with high-resolution Satellite images in planning and decision-making will have a negative impact in the long term by not being able to understand the temporary and long-term changes occurring in the global market especially in the midst of intense competition. The analysis of high-resolution satellite images for detection the urban growth associated with identify buildings type (villas, apartments, mall, etc.) and its construction level will provide a clear vision for the current market size and create more accurate expectations, this information will not be available through other methods to helps the decision makers for better analyse situation to generate a forecast based on more accurate data, and contribute to the selection of the best location for the establishment of services.

In general Arab and Middle East countries knowledge about Geomarketing is very limited in volume, and it is unclear how used in the organizations. Therefore this research presents the use of satellite images in Geomarketing in:

- a) Improving market size reading.
- b) thinking at micro-geographic area
- c) How it supports decision-making?
- d) How Geomarketing should use in the future?
- e) How will marketing strategy improve?

This study was carried out in the north of Riyadh City as shown in Figure (1.2). In the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in an area that has a fast growing and forms the vital area of the city, with the aim of improving plans and determining market size based on spatial data. Many programs and projects may falter in the absence of the accurate data that reflect the current reality that enables the governmental authorities and companies of an Evaluate the needs of the community, determine market size and forecast for the future. Therefore, government agencies and companies are looking forward to having the data to help them to address the challenges and create appropriate plans to meet the community requirements. However, current data and methodologies can't solve the demands and needs of each geographical area. The proposed method will help decision-makers in building and developing plans more effectively and include the following.

1.3. Objective

The objective of this study is as follow:

1. To determine the effect of adding geospatial information to the marketing strategy.
2. To determine market size and develop forecasting methodology by using remote sensing
3. To improve the best site location methodology by Geomarketing.

1.4. Scope of Study

The overarching purpose of this research to examine using the High-resolution satellite images in Geomarketing and improve marketing strategy with a combination of other factors to have better results by distinguishing the buildings type (existing and new) and support decision-maker in their decisions.

Will study the impact of buildings growth and the units per buildings to the market size for the studying products. This growth also affects the population increasing so we will study the community who live or can live in this area by having information about the family member. The population density will determine according to this methodology. Methodology.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Building Extraction

Jin used object-oriented segmentation and classification methodology by using texture, characteristics, feature, shape feature to extract the building in remote sensing images (Jin, 2012). Jian used object-oriented classification to have individual object-classes, and fuzzy determined rules system to be created for earthquake collapsed building extraction (Jian, 2013). Huang and lot of researcher used many indexes to extracted the building as result of the different scale of different type building and merged the results as a whole, Suggested novel morphological building index for automatic building extraction by using high-resolution images with optimization and improvements (Huang and Zhang, 2011), Jian yang used another method to extract the building information by combination the contoured transform and PCNN segmentation algorithm to obtain the multiscale and multidirectional characteristic of the building. Other efforts have been made to extract buildings in automated ways. Applied the Perceptual grouping way to obtain the building.

Lin and Nevatia detected the edges of the image to find the parallel lines from the edges. After that, they searched for the parallel lines to find a rectangle which meets the geometric and projective constraints as the building object, (Lin and Nevatia, 1998). A study proposed a building extraction method by combining edge preserving, smoothing bilateral filter with the line segment detector. Wang used a filtration for smooth the original satellite image, detected the line segments and grouped the lines to construct a rectangular building, so these methods are suitable for extracting simple square buildings, (Wang, 2015)

Li et. al. suggested to a hierarchical extraction style with a visual graphical topic model embedded to extract building with a complex or simple pattern. In this method, buildings with simple rectangular pattern and non-buildings were detected and taken to be the training set firstly. Then a learned semantic feature mapping and discriminative model were used to extract complex buildings, (Li et al, 2014).

Recent research done by Yihua Tan, Yujie Yu is that adopted an energy minimization model for semi-automatic building extraction from VHR imagery. The proposed framework consists of two main stages: generating foreground and background area, minimizing the energy function, (Yihua Tan, Yujie Yu, 2016). The classification of high-resolution images was studied by a lot of researchers More recently, finer texture and more certain boundaries of the building can be obtained from HSR imagery and applied to build extraction, (Ok, 2013). So it is still difficult to discern building types from high-resolution images by computers programs because it is hard to find appropriate segmenting scales to completely capture even an individual building from complex patterns of combining pixels,(Zhang 2015), Elevation data and building contours have also applied in classification of building type. Airborne light detection and ranging (LiDAR) is particularly useful to collect the elevation data for the expression of building structural characteristics, (Kraus and Pfeifer, 1998).

In EMRS-SBP scheme, (Extended multiresolution segmentation) EMRS serves to guide the design of descriptor and SBP to generate a more natural classification is used for the classification of urban building type, (Junfei and Jinhua, 2017). Change detection for remote sensing images has been applied to many fields, such as urban area and so on. It has drawn great attention in recent years since it is an efficient way to find the differences between images with different dates, typical methods often firstly consider spectral features and then use threshold segmentation to detect the change. However, the thresholds are usually determined by experience, which brings about a series of problems, (Wen, Huang, 2016), Huo, J. Cheng introduced two different multiscale fusion strategies conducted the experiments on QuickBird high-resolution remote sensing images and completed the object-oriented change detection. But the robustness of this algorithm is not good enough, (Huo, Cheng, 2008).

Qingle Guo and others studied a new method which is a multiscale segmentation and decision-level fusion, Multiscale segmentation refers to segmenting the same image in different scales, and the segmentation results can reveal the multiscale land-cover features and spatial structure information of images, (Qingle Guo, Junping Zhang, 2017).

2.2. GIS

GIS used to support the decision maker in many fields like working to decrease food waste, (San Martin1 2017), decision making is based on numerous data concerning the problem. It has been estimated that 80% of data used by managers and decision makers are geographical (spatial) in nature, (Worrall 1991), GIS using in the most critical and far-reaching decisions which faced by operations managers is deciding where to locate new industrial facilities. This is a strategic decision involving irreversible allocation of the firm's capital, (Bhatnagar & Sohal, 2005), GIS is tools to solve the spatial decision problem typically includes a large set of feasible alternatives, (Rikalovic and Aleksandar, 2014).

Amparo BAVIERA-PUIG told Geomarketing viewpoint, and the model shows that sociodemographic characteristics of the supermarket's trade area affect firms' location strategies, (Amparo Baviera-Puig, Juan Buitrago, 2016).

2.3. Forecasting

Arvydas Jadevicius and Simon Huston studied statistical estimates to confirm the claim that goodness-of-fit does not imply good forecasting performance and that increased model complexity does not necessarily yield greater forecasting accuracy. This, therefore, calls for the adoption of a Laconic or "Keep It Sensibly Simple" modelling approach. In other words, the recommendation is for analysts to make forecasts user-friendly so that they are easy to Use and understand. Researchers should put simplicity at the core of their

2.4. Best Site Location

The geographic information system can combine spatial data, especially competitor sites, with solutions designed to help open a new facility to enhance the competitiveness of the new entity.

Competitive sites consist of several criteria and are primarily related to consumers and service providers. Here, customer behavior must be considered so that we can meet their demands so that they can have all their requirements in one place (Rafael Suárez, 2012)

The opening of a new branch for any company or service is one of the critical works that requires careful study and depends on scientific methodologies in which the review of the situation in various aspects to mitigate any risks that may result from the expansion of activity

The population density that will be used to determine the new location has been studied based on the data obtained from the Statistics Authority (Norat Roig, 2013)

“Qiming” noted that the opening of a new branch for any company is an important decision that should be considered carefully. He described the problem and presented solutions and suggestions to guide users to find the best site. Initially, he suggested a solution without looking at the competitors and then propose another solution, considering the threat resulting from competitor’s activities, he used GIS to designing and study these solutions (Qiming Tian, 2009)

“Xuefeng” Used ArcGIS Geoprocessing to develop spatial analysis modeling and decision making by using implementation technology, modeling and multiple options using ARC GIS, using the classification and reclassification method, and calculating the required spaces to set up the new branch within the conditions and result (Xuefeng, 2010)

“Kazem” presented a study to select the best location for parking as a result of the traffic jam of Tehran city and performed the study of land use and peak areas of traffic and restrictions that prevent the establishment of this position such as cultural restrictions and historical monuments, all those features have been added all to the maps to determine the outputs that correspond with Determine the best location for parking (Kazem, 2015).

CHPATER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

In this section, we will study the data used, the sources of these data, and how it will be processed and used in a manner appropriate to this study, what the variables which used and how can it affect the study, also explain the software that used. What are the satellite data and spatial data, their dates, how can estimate the population by using Remotes sensing, and how we can expect market size for a given product?

3.2. Data Collection

3.2.1. Remote Sensing Data

The primary data used to conduct this study is the Remote sensing data for determining to the urban growth that will require the use of two satellite images in two different dates for the studying area, the specification for it was:

- Satellite: Optical Spot 6
- Resolution: 1.5 m, colour

The first image: its date was January 2016, itis used to create a feature class containing all the existing buildings at that date and classified it according to the building type and construction level.

The second image, figure (3.1): its date was October 2016, itis used to create a feature class containing the new buildings which constructed after the date of the first image in order to know the exact number of new buildings that were created in the study area and which classified according to the building type and construction level, The construction level is:

- a) Basements
- b) Under construction
- c) Construction completed

Here we have the all the building in the studying area, existing and new which classified depend on a field observation (explained in the methodology)

Spot Satellite image for Riyadh city

0 12.525 50 75 100
Meters

Figure 3.1. Shown Spot 1.5 m Satellite Image

3.2.2 Surveys

Since one of the objectives of this study aims to increase the accuracy of the identify market size by remote sensing, one of the building materials products was studied to estimate the expected demand of these products (switches and sockets) during a specific period and determine the cumulative demand. To achieve this goal, a field survey of a sample of electricians and contractors (50 people) was conducted in the study area to determine the average need for each building type. (Villa, apartment, palace, mall, mosque,..) For these products during the finishing phase

The survey included the following questions:

1. The average number of pieces (switches and sockets) needed by each type of buildings, (Table 3.1).
2. The expected time for these products to installing to those buildings type, table (3.2).

Table 3.1. The Average Number of Pieces For Each Building Type

Buildings type	Switches Average (pieces)
villa	193.66
Apartment	771.37
Esteraha	48.63
Mosque	104.67
tower	4188.44
Gas station	93.22
Industry	300
School	425.56
Mall	227.25
showroom	351.38
Palace	2000
warehouse	50
Governmental	1613.25

Table 3.2. The Duration of The Stage For Building Type

Building type	Duration of the stage(month)		
	Basement	Under construction	construction completed
Apartment	6	12	24
Esteraha	3	6	12
Gas Station	3	6	12
Governmental	6	12	24
Mall	6	12	24
Mosque	6	12	24
Palace	6	12	24
School	6	12	24
Showroom	3	6	12
Tower	6	12	24
villa	3	6	12
warehouse	3	6	12

3.2.3. Open Street Map

The road network in the study area was extracted using the open Street map where the road network in the area was extracted, checked, completed and classified into primary and secondary roads to help classify the buildings where apartments are often built on the main roads, while the villas are inside districts alongside the secondary roads, the roads also help to demarcate the boundaries of the micro-geographic area, the roads also will be taken into consideration for choosing the best location, Figure (3.2).

Figure 3.2. Road Network in The Study Area

3.2.4. Nielsen Data

Nielsen data used to estimate Milk market size as FMCG products by using Remote sensing data at the micro-geographic area.

- a) The average per capita consumption of milk per day in Riyadh was 0.11 litres while in Saudi Arabia it is 0.09 litres per day in 2016 (Nielsen company)
- b) Market size includes white/plain and flavoured milk. Excludes powder milk & fermented milk drinks (Laban or yogurt)

c) This study only for residential sectors (Villas, Apartments, Palaces)

The following table shows the total consumption in Saudi Arabia and Riyadh City

Table 3.3. Milk Consumption in KSA and Riyadh City (Nielsen data)

KSA -MILK CONSUMPTION (Million Litre/ year)	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Fresh Milk	506.8	458.1	483.5	518.7	550.3	579.7
Growth (%)	9.40%	-9.60%	5.50%	7.30%	6.10%	5.40%
Total KSA	807.4	888.6	945.1	997.7	1034	1077
Growth (%)	9.30%	10.10%	6.40%	5.60%	3.70%	4.10%
RIYADH ONLY	283	311	331	349	362	377

3.3. Variables

3.3.1. Buildings

Buildings Growth means Growth in market demand for a lot of products like buildings materials; also the population will live in the new buildings which food, water, and Milk will necessary for them, this variable will have it by Satellite images analysis.

3.3.2. Number of Residential Units Per Residential Buildings Type

This variable changes according to the city and districts, it means the number of units that each residential building type contain, this factor info obtained from the authority of statics.

3.3.3. Family Member

It's a critical variable to estimate the population in the study area which helps to calculate the expected FMCG demand like Milk market size, the family member obtained from the authority of statics.

3.3.4. Vacant Buildings Percentage

According to the authority of statics, there were 12 % of vacant residential units in Riyadh in 2016 which should consider it when calculating the population in the studying area, and this factor affects the expected community so when this factor increase that is mean the population will decrease.

3.3.5. Required Time for Products Installation

This variable is necessary to estimate the required time that each building type needs to install the products or required time that the residential buildings ready for living.

This variable has been got it from a survey of the experience of contractors and electricians, table (3.2), when this variable increase the required time for products installation will increase and also the require time for living.

Methodology

The geographical information (GIS) system used in this study in order to identify the existing and new buildings which determined depends on the experience and the images interpretation by manual digitizing. A point placed in front of each building and its classification according to the building type and the construction level, and this done for the images dated at January 2016 and October 2016 .

The types of buildings determined according to the following (the Photographs at the appendices):

- a) The majority of the buildings that are next to the main roads are apartments, which are the features of the building systems in Saudi Arabia, especially in the main cities.
- b) Villas located inside the districts next to secondary roads.
- c) The Esteraha is a building consisting of a few rooms and one floor, it has a small garden with a pool and usually rented during the holidays.
- d) Towers: It is a high building with more than ten floors like hotels that typically located next to some of the main roads such as King Abdul Aziz Road or the Northern Ring.
- e) Mosques: Its shape is distinctive, especially the towards of Mihrab to the Qibla
- f) Gas station.
- g) Malls: which occupy large areas.

- h) Showrooms: usually characterized by the large building and its positions near to the main roads.
- i) Schools and government buildings: characterized by the occupied area and by the method of construction, consisting of four blocks in general and especially for schools.
- j) Palaces and large villas: characterized by the large occupied area which located inside the districts green areas within it.

All types of buildings identified by the satellite image and classified according to the construction level, table (3.2) and the construction level that includes:

- a) Basement
- b) Under construction
- c) Construction is complete

For example, to explain this methodology to determine the market size, we can apply it to calculate the market needs for two kinds of products (FMCG like Milk and building materials like switches and sockets).

In the following will process and study:

- a) Estimating the population in the study area at the Micro-Geographic area levels to using it to estimate the demand for a wide range of services and products.
- b) Estimate the Milk market size and cumulative milk market size at the Micro-Geographic area levels.
- c) Estimate the material of products (switches and sockets) market size and cumulative market size the Micro-Geographic area levels.
- d) Carry out analysis to select the best site location for new services depend on the population density which estimated by using satellite images.

3.4. Used Software

3.4.1. ARC GIS 10.1

ARC GIS (Geographic Information Stem) is a computer-based system that collects, maintains, stores, analyses, outputs and distributes data and spatial information? These

systems collect, input, process, analyse, display and produce spatial and descriptive information for specific objectives, and assist planning and decision-making concerning agriculture, urban planning, housing expansion, as well as reading the infrastructure of any city through the creation of called Layers. This system introduces geographic information (maps, aerial photographs, and satellite images), descriptors (names, tables), processing them (revising the error), storing them, retrieving them, analysing them, and analysing them on a computer screen or on paper in the form of maps. , Reports, and graphs.

GIS helps to answer many of the specific questions of specificity (e.g., what is the agricultural pattern, what types of suitable crops to cultivate in the farm unit), measurements, location (What is the relationship between population distribution and Milk or water market size) and hydrological scenarios (what happens if the water used for irrigation).

3.4.2. Erdas Imagine

Erdas Imagine (Earth Resource Development Assessment System) Is a digital image processing software used for analysis and study the satellite imagery, By using it for extraction of Digital Number values of the pixels of the image, and Import export raster's and vectors satellite image, working with various bands of satellite data, to perform detailed analysis of multiple objects and information using the pattern recognition technique, Land use land cover analysis. Everything you do on Erdas Imagine has a unique concept of Visual Interpretation of satellite imagery.

3.5. Methodology

3.5.1. Workflow

This work started after selecting the studying area which the methodology will be applying to study it, we have to choose the period that we will investigate it then the suitable satellite images which be optical which will be used to extract existing buildings from the older image then determine the growth by extract the new buildings from the latest image, here we should have information about the family member per building unit

or FMCG daily consumption (Milk) and buildings needs from the products for each building type to determine the market size and improve the forecasting. The following flowchart explains the process.

Figure 3.3 Process Workflow

3.5.2. Satellite Images Analyses

3.5.2.1. January 2016 Satellite Images

The existing construction opportunities in the study area have been extracted to determine the number of existing buildings and classify it according to the building type.

The buildings which under construction were not considered as part of the existing buildings on that date and were therefore considered part of the subsequent buildings.

A description of the existing building included in its attribute table which included the building type and construction level (here the construction stage is considered as completed), Table (3.4) shows the total existing building that detected in January 2016 by Satellite images analysis.

Table 3.4. Total Buildings Scanned in January With its Building Type

Building type	Number of existing buildings	percentage %
villa	44603	88.77
Apartment	3345	6.66
Esteraha	914	1.82
Showroom	526	1.05
Palace	277	0.55
Mosque	237	0.47
School	93	0.19
warehouse	88	0.18
Tower	85	0.17
Gas Station	43	0.09
Governmental	20	0.04
Compound	6	0.01
Industry	3	0.01
Mall	3	0.01
Grand Total	50243	100%

Figure 3.4 Buildings Type Segmentation For January 2016 Buildings.

Table (3.4) and figure (3.4) show that the villas reflect 89% of the existing buildings while the Apartments reflect only 8%

3.5.2.2. October 2016 Satellite Images

The analysis of the following satellite image dating to October 2016 will determine the growth and trends in the study area; the new buildings classified according to the buildings type and construction level, Table (3.5).

Figure 3.5 Buildings Type Segmentation for October 2016 Buildings

Table 3.5. Total Buildings Scanned in October 2016 With its Building Type

Building type	Number of new buildings	percentage %
villa	3626	84.96
Apartment	429	10.05
Showroom	94	2.20
Esteraha	57	1.34
Palace	18	0.42
Mosque	15	0.35
School	9	0.21
Gas Station	8	0.19
Tower	5	0.12
Governmental	3	0.07
warehouse	2	0.05
Compound	1	0.02
Mall	1	0.02
Industry	0	0.00
Grand Total	4268	100%

Also, the majority of the new buildings consist of villas by 85 %, apartments 10 % while the other buildings type include the remains percentage.

3.5.3. Micro-Geographic Segmentation

The study area was divided into Small districts (micro-Geographic area) to identifying the growth at this level to understand the requirements for those areas by determining the business volume and improve the planning. The main roads were selected as the borders for those micro-Geographic areas and labelled with unique numbers starting from 1 to 44, the areas for those districts vary from 2.3 Sq. to 7.7 Sq., only one district its area 23.8 sq. Which contain a large university, districts 25.

Figure 3.6 Micro-Geographic Area Segmentations

3.5.4. Population

Determine the building type and construction level will be valuable for urban area planning and improve business, in other meaning, remote sensing will give us new tool by identifying the population in the districts and micro-geographic area by having information about the total Buildings with its geospatial information, so the buildings will give us the reading and indicator for the population. By using the geospatial data, we will be able to have more accurate information about the community in the studying area and market needs at the districts level. Population information will support decision makers in many sectors (Governmental, business...) to have the right decision depending on the new data.

The total Buildings in January 2016 was 50243 buildings, the residential buildings were 48225 (95.98 % from total), While total new buildings in October 2016 was 4268 buildings, the residential buildings in October were 4037 Buildings (95.43 % from total). According to the 2013 census (Authority of statics) In KSA:

- a) The average units per villa are 3.5 units. (V)
- b) The average units per Apartment are 15.5 units. (A)
- c) The average units per palace are 1 units. (P)
- d) The average population per units is 5.97 person per units. (AVE)
- e) Percentage of non-inhabited buildings in Riyadh is 12 % (88% inhabited). (E).

General Note: depend on 2013 census:

- a- In general, the ground floor in villas is occupied by a Saudi family which have a driver and housekeeper at 50%.

Population in a villa

$$\text{POP VI} = (V * \text{AVE}) + [(\text{driver} + \text{housekeeper}) * 50\%] * E \quad 3.1$$

$$= (3.5 * 5.97) + [(\text{driver} + \text{housekeeper}) * 50\%] * 88\% = 19.26 \text{ person}$$

- b- 38 % of Apartments population is Saudi (25 % of this Saudi segments has a housekeeper)

Population in Apartment

$$\text{POPAPA} = \{(A * \text{AVE}) + [(A * \text{AVE}) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * E \quad 3.2$$

$$= \{(15.5 * 5.97) + [(15.5 * 5.98) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * 88\% = (92.69 + 8.790825) * 88\%$$

$$= 89.16 \text{ person}$$

c- Population in Palace

$$\text{POP PA} = (P * \text{AVE}) + (\text{Driver} + \text{housekeeper} + \text{cooker} + \text{gardener}) * E \quad 3.3$$

$$= (1 * 5.97) + (\text{Driver} + \text{housekeeper} + \text{cooker} + \text{gardener}) * 88\% = (5.98 + 4) * 88\% = 8.77 \text{ person.}$$

Table (3.6) Average Number of Units per Residential Type and Population per Building Type

Building type	Average No. units	Average population per building type
Apartment	15.5	89.16
Villa	3.5	19.26
Palace	1	8.77

After digitizing the existing and new buildings, will give it unique identity by GIS tools, this identity contains: Micro-Geographic code and coordinate system, the other information entered manually during the digitizing like building type and stage.

3.6. Discussion

What we have now, while digitizing the building will have the required information:

- a) Districts code: to know how much building in each districts.
- b) Coordinate system: to create geospatial data
- c) Building type: to Determine the number and type of buildings in each district, if we know the average population in each building type then will determine the population in each district and the study area, here we can expect the milk market size as FMCG study product, or the required products for each building type then expect the potential market size in district and area.

- d) Building stage: This information was necessary to determine the required time for each building type to install the products or ready for living. In this study, I hypothesized that they needed time for products installing is the same time that the building will be prepared to live (the time difference will be ignored). This information is useful for the planning team and logistics operation.

3.7. Conclusion

The study area in this section has determined and its general specification and the data which used in this research. Also, The methodology that used to extract and classify the construction, the relationship between the data collected with the buildings were explained to determine Building needs to products or the expected population for each building then at districts levels.

CHAPTER .4

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Introduction

In this chapter will study how we can use this methodology to determine the population at districts level and the expected growth, calculate the cumulative number of community in a specific time; also the population estimation will use to develop a methodology to determine the best site location in the study area. The expected need for an FMCG product (Milk) in the study area will be estimated at the Micro-Geographic level and the expected growth according to time with the cumulative needs for the same periods. Also, determine the growth will help us to calculate the building needs from materials products and applying this methodology to estimate (Switches and sockets) market size.

Population analysis.

If we take into account the General notes, table (3.5) and 2013 census, we can expect the population in the residential buildings (Villa, Apartment, and palace) then by using the building stage the population growth and cumulative growth will calculate accordingly. In the following the expected population which their buildings were detected by satellite image in January 2016 will be studying and analysing, then the predicted population which can live in the buildings which scanned by satellite image in October 2016 (nine-month difference).

In addition to buildings type, the buildings that extracted by October satellite image will classify to:

- a) Completed building: it is ready for a living or installs material products.
- b) Under construction buildings: it will be prepared for living or installing after a period which differs according to building type.
- c) Basement Buildings: it will be ready for living or installing after a period which changes according to building type. But will take time more than the buildings in the previous stage.

4.1.1. January 2016 Population

The residential buildings that extracted by January 2016 satellite images shown in the following Table (4.1). It explains the number of residential buildings with the average population in those building according to building type, and this estimation depends on the table (3.6).

Table 4.1 Expected Population in the Study Area According to Building Type

Building type	NO. of building	Average population per building type (person)	Total population (person)
Villa	44603	19.2676	859392
Apartment	3345	89.16672	298262
Palace	277	8.7809	2432
Sum			1160086

The majority of people lives in Villas while who lives in Palace approaching zero, Figure (4.1)

Figure 4.1 People Segmentation at January 2016

Now we will search where those people live? In which district? Where the highest population which will mark as the most upper potential market size. GIS will help to give each building the district code which located in, here will know how much buildings in

each district and how much people in each district. This methodology will help the decision makers to have a good view of the expected demand in the area and change their plan accordingly.

Table 4.2. Expected Population at January 2016

District	Building type			expected pop per Building type			Grand Total
	Apartment	Palace	Villa	Apartment	Palace	Villa	
1	176	20	1928	15693.34	175.62	37147.93	53016.90
2	205	10	2692	18279.18	87.81	51868.38	70235.37
3	183	11	2365	16317.51	96.59	45567.87	61981.98
4	148	49	1618	13196.68	430.27	31174.98	44801.92
5	99	5	729	8827.51	43.90	14046.08	22917.49
6	20	36	871	1783.33	316.11	16782.08	18881.53
7	9	16	783	802.50	140.50	15086.53	16029.53
8	31	17	608	2764.17	149.28	11714.70	14628.15
9	159	1	430	14177.51	8.78	8285.07	22471.36
10	576	4	2030	51360.03	35.12	39113.23	90508.39
11	130	15	1775	11591.67	131.71	34199.99	45923.38
12	122	14	2363	10878.34	122.93	45529.34	56530.61
13	37	6	1732	3299.17	52.69	33371.48	36723.34
14	34	0	266	3031.67	0.00	5125.18	8156.85
15	79	5	3192	7044.17	43.90	61502.18	68590.26
16	194	6	3243	17298.34	52.69	62484.83	79835.86
17	239	21	1701	21310.85	184.40	32774.19	54269.44
18	8	3	400	713.33	26.34	7707.04	8446.72
19	9	5	418	802.50	43.90	8053.86	8900.26
20	135	1	773	12037.51	8.78	14893.85	26940.14
21	163	7	1421	14534.18	61.47	27379.26	41974.90
22	110	6	3234	9808.34	52.69	62311.42	72172.44
23	87	4	2439	7757.51	35.12	46993.68	54786.31
24	20	0	337	1783.33	0.00	6493.18	8276.52
25	100	0	909	8916.67	0.00	17514.25	26430.92
26	1	0	85	89.17	0.00	1637.75	1726.91
27	17	0	365	1515.83	0.00	7032.67	8548.51
28	4	0	353	356.67	0.00	6801.46	7158.13
29	2	0	184	178.33	0.00	3545.24	3723.57
30	16	4	384	1426.67	35.12	7398.76	8860.55
31	41	1	612	3655.84	8.78	11791.77	15456.39
32	0	0	37	0.00	0.00	712.90	712.90
33	0	0	41	0.00	0.00	789.97	789.97
35	2	0	14	178.33	0.00	269.75	448.08
36	4	0	211	356.67	0.00	4065.46	4422.13
37	48	2	1604	4280.00	17.56	30905.23	35202.80
38	12	2	579	1070.00	17.56	11155.94	12243.50
39	2	1	329	178.33	8.78	6339.04	6526.15
40	58	0	449	5171.67	0.00	8651.15	13822.82
41	19	2	357	1694.17	17.56	6878.53	8590.26
42	17	0	150	1515.83	0.00	2890.14	4405.97
43	27	2	406	2407.50	17.56	7822.65	10247.71
44	2	1	186	178.33	8.78	3583.77	3770.89
Grand Total	3345	277	44603	298262.70	2432	859392	1160087

Figure 4.2 Expected Population at January 2016.

Map analysis: This figure shows the expected population according to January buildings, districts with dark blue are the highest population density while the red colour reflects the lowest.

4.1.2. October 2016 Population

The urban growth in the study area will associate with an increase in the population who will live in the new buildings according to the completion of those constructions which

was built after January 2016 and detected at October 2016 Satellite image. The whole buildings were 4073 while the residential was 4268 buildings. Below table explain the expected population that can live in those buildings as listed in Table (4.3).

Table 4.3 Expected Population According to Buildings Scanned at October 2016

District	Building type			expected pop per Building type (person)			Grand Total
	Apartment	Palace	villa	Apartment	Palace	villa	
1	3		27	267.50		520.23	787.73
2	7		64	624.17		1233.13	1857.29
3	6		60	535.00		1156.06	1691.06
4	3		11	267.50		211.94	479.44
5			20			385.35	385.35
6	3		18	267.50		346.82	614.32
7		2	47		17.56	905.58	923.14
8	1	4	54	89.17	35.12	1040.45	1164.74
9	5		9	445.83		173.41	619.24
10	14		16	1248.33		308.28	1556.62
11	3		23	267.50		443.15	710.65
12	2		45	178.33		867.04	1045.38
13	5	9	101	445.83	79.03	1946.03	2470.89
14	6		58	535.00		1117.52	1652.52
15	31		130	2764.17		2504.79	5268.96
16	5		38	445.83		732.17	1178.00
17	7		42	624.17		809.24	1433.41
18	3	1	77	267.50	8.78	1483.61	1759.89
19	6		37	535.00		712.90	1247.90
20	28		145	2496.67		2793.80	5290.47
21	15		69	1337.50		1329.46	2666.97
22	8		44	713.33		847.77	1561.11
23	23		165	2050.83		3179.15	5229.99
24	16		141	1426.67		2716.73	4143.40
25	34		211	3031.67		4065.46	7097.13
26	17		97	1515.83		1868.96	3384.79
27	24		259	2140.00		4990.31	7130.31
28			29			558.76	558.76
29	1		3	89.17		57.80	146.97
30	13		41	1159.17		789.97	1949.14
31	14		117	1248.33		2254.31	3502.64
32			23			443.15	443.15
33			57			1098.25	1098.25
35	1		17	89.17		327.55	416.72
36	1		14	89.17		269.75	358.91
37	6		151	535.00		2909.41	3444.41
38	20		459	1783.33		8843.83	10627.16
39			133			2562.59	2562.59
40	39		225	3477.50		4335.21	7812.71
41	19		84	1694.17		1618.48	3312.65
42	8		34	713.33		655.10	1368.43
43	30	2	120	2675.00	17.56	2312.11	5004.68
44	2		111	178.33		2138.70	2317.04
Grand Total	429	18	3626	38252.53	158.06	69864.32	108274.90

Figure 4.3 Expected Population at October 2016.

Map analysis: This figure shows the expected population according to October 2016 buildings, districts with dark blue are the highest population density while the red color reflects the lowest. But this map does not reflect the reality because there are a different building construction stages which should consider it during the analysis. Its meaning the duration to complete the construction should be taking in our account, and this will let us determine the expected population growth in the following periods.

The details of the residential buildings according to its construction stage which detected in October image is shown in the table (4.4), If we take into account the table (3.2) which

explain the building duration) and table (4.4 below), the results are the constructions which will be ready to living depending on the required time to complete, which is helping to identify the buildings that will be ready for living in that time and its population capacity, table (4.5).

Table 4.4 Total Buildings for October 2016 Contractions With its Buildings Stage

Building type	Construction level			Grand Total
	Basement	Under construction	construction completed	
Apartment	81	127	221	429
Palace	6	9	3	18
villa	764	640	2222	3626
Grand Total	851	776	2446	4073

This table show us the expected population after three months, six months, one and two years for October buildings depending on the districts,

After three months (starting from October 2016) the expected of the new population is 62545 person, after six months the expected population will increase by 12331 people and so on, the total expected increase in population 108275 Depending on the October buildings.

Table 4.5 Expected Population According to The Construction Stage for October Buildings.

District	Expected population according to the construction stage for October buildings (person)				
	Three Month	Six Month	One Year	Two Year	Total population two years later
1	602	19	166		788
2	1351	96	320	89	1857
3	1332	77	193	89	1691
4	116	96	268		479
5	308		77		385
6	467		58	89	614
7	385	58	462	18	923
8	599	135	413	18	1165
9	383	19	128	89	619
10	658	58	574	268	1557
11	205	212	294		711
12	841	58	58	89	1045
13	1305	328	750	89	2471
14	949	58	557	89	1653
15	3746	308	947	268	5269
16	865	96	128	89	1178
17	1043	116	186	89	1433
18	995	212	455	98	1760
19	576	39	634		1248
20	2867	385	1593	446	5291
21	1573	443	561	89	2667
22	1164	135	263		1561
23	3180	347	1169	535	5230
24	2300	559	660	624	4143
25	4103	713	1836	446	7097
26	1896	328	626	535	3385
27	3782	925	1800	624	7130
28	193	308	58		559
29	19	39	89		147
30	641	135	906	268	1949
31	1696	135	1494	178	3503
32	19	39	385		443
33	328	231	540		1098
35	96	116	205		417
36	186	116	58		359
37	1727	751	699	268	3444
38	7320	1753	1376	178	10627
39	1580	424	559		2563
40	5153	732	1571	357	7813
41	1874	308	952	178	3313
42	773	96	320	178	1368
43	2375	829	990	811	5005
44	976	501	751	89	2317
Total population	62545	12331	26124	7275	108275

Figure 4.4 Expected Population According to the Construction Stage for October Buildings.

Figure 4.4 analysis: the majority of population growth depends on October buildings will be after three months starting from October 2016, while the lowest growth will be two years later beginning in October 2016. The results in Table (4.5) will be very clear and fantastic if we can reflect it, to visual maps to be more readable, maps (4.5 to 4.8)

Figure 4.5 The Expected Increase in Population Three Months Later per Districts

Figure 4.6 The Expected Increase in Population Six Months Later per Districts

Figure 4.7 The Expected Increase in Population One Year Later per Districts

Figure 4.8 the Expected Increase in Population Two Years Later per Districts

Maps analysis: The figures (4.5 to 4.8) shows the expected population increases according to October 2016 buildings for the periods three months to two years, districts with dark blue are the highest population growth while the red colour reflects the lowest.

4.2. Cumulative Population

Furthermore, if we want to know the cumulative population for the same periods (three months, six months, one year and two years), namely the expected population growth after three months was 1874 but the cumulative population is the population living in the studying area is the current population (January 2016) plus the expected population growth after three months 1160087 plus 62545 this equal to 1222632 people.

By applying this equation:

$$\text{CUM (n)} = \text{POP (Current)} + \text{Ex POP (n)} \quad 4.1$$

n = after three month, Ex POP (n) = expected population growth after (n) period

POP (current) = January 2016

CUM (3) = 1160087 + 62545 = 1222632 person

While the six-month population cumulative is three months cumulative plus six months expected growth 1222632 +12331= 1234963 people.

It is essential for forecasting and planning; the decision makers will know with reliability and accuracy what the region needs to, what the market size when the market needs the services, the government will be able to improve its planning to meet the user's requirements.

Table 4.6 Expected Cumulative Population According to the Construction Stage for
Total Buildings

District	January population	October Buildings influences			
		Three Month cumulative	Six Month cumulative	One Year cumulative	Two Year cumulative
1	53017	53619	53638	53805	53805
2	70235	71587	71683	72003	72093
3	61982	63314	63391	63584	63673
4	44802	44918	45014	45281	45281
5	22917	23226	23226	23303	23303
6	18882	19349	19349	19407	19496
7	16030	16415	16473	16935	16953
8	14628	15227	15362	15775	15793
9	22471	22854	22874	23001	23091
10	90508	91166	91224	91798	92065
11	45923	46128	46340	46634	46634
12	56531	57371	57429	57487	57576
13	36723	38028	38356	39105	39194
14	8157	9106	9164	9720	9809
15	68590	72337	72645	73592	73859
16	79836	80701	80797	80925	81014
17	54269	55313	55428	55614	55703
18	8447	9441	9653	10109	10207
19	8900	9476	9515	10148	10148
20	26940	29807	30192	31785	32231
21	41975	43548	43991	44553	44642
22	72172	73336	73471	73734	73734
23	54786	57966	58313	59481	60016
24	8277	10577	11136	11796	12420
25	26431	30534	31246	33082	33528
26	1727	3623	3950	4577	5112
27	8459	12241	13166	15055	15679
28	7158	7351	7659	7717	7717
29	3724	3743	3781	3871	3871
30	8861	9501	9636	10542	10810
31	15456	17152	17287	18781	18959
32	713	732	771	1156	1156
33	790	1118	1349	1888	1888
35	448	544	660	865	865
36	4422	4608	4723	4781	4781
37	35203	36930	37681	38380	38647
38	12056	19376	21130	22692	22871
39	6526	8106	8530	9089	9089
40	13734	18887	19619	21279	21636
41	8590	10465	10773	11725	11903
42	4406	5179	5276	5596	5774
43	10159	12533	13362	14441	15252
44	3771	4746	5247	5999	6088
Total population	1159633	1222178	1234509	1261087	1268363

Figure 4.9 Expected Cumulative Population According to the Construction Stage for Total Buildings

Figure 4.9 analysis: the charts show us that the highest population cumulative was two years later after October 2016 while the lowest population cumulative was three months later after October 2016.

Figure 4.10 The Expected Cumulative Population one Years Later

Figure 4.11 The Expected Cumulative Population Two Years Later

Maps analysis: The figures (4.10 and 4.11) shows the expected cumulative population which calculated for all buildings that detected in January and October 2016, districts with dark blue are the highest population growth while the red colour reflects the lowest.

4.3. Milk Market Size

The information that obtained from Satellite images and Geomarketing which provide information about the existing buildings which detected at January 2016 and new buildings which built after January 2016 and detected at October 2016, these information will support the business and industry with the new tools which gives the required data about the new business volume with associated geospatial data for better understanding about the market situations, market size and the potential market, potential manpower or any required information that can support the decision makers. The big challenge for the Science and the researchers are using it in industry or business, we studied the population forecasting according to the periods and micro-geographic areas, and this will be valuable for studying FMCG products like Milk. Which is an essential strategic product to find out how much people need it and what time it takes to need it, this kind of FMCG cannot

keep for a long time it would, therefore, be useful to know how much people will need (Quantity), where and when? This is a challenge to improve planning, control production to meet the need of people for fresh milk daily and prevent any waste in the resources.

4.3.1. January 2016 Milk Market size

We will discuss in the following the milk market size depending on the population, which was estimated based on the existing buildings in the previous sections. The estimation population at January 2016 was 1160087 person in the studying area, table (4.2), by take it in our account and consider the Nielsen survey (3.3). The following table (4.7) explains the milk consumption daily, and yearly in the study area for the population which lives in January 2016 buildings, we need this total volume to understand the expected market size Regardless of the subsequent increase in the population which we will study it for October buildings.

Table 4.7 Expected Daily and Yearly Milk Consumption According to January Buildings

District	Yearly Consumption(L)	Daily Consumption(L)
1	2128628.36	5831.86
2	2819950.01	7725.89
3	2488576.31	6818.02
4	1798797.04	4928.21
5	920137.26	2520.92
6	758093.36	2076.97
7	643585.49	1763.25
8	587320.04	1609.1
9	902225.04	2471.85
10	3633911.7	9955.92
11	1843823.65	5051.57
12	2269704.1	6218.37
13	1474442.01	4039.57
14	327497.54	897.25
15	2753898.75	7544.93
16	3205409.67	8781.94
17	2178917.82	5969.64
18	339135.67	929.14
19	357345.52	979.03
20	1081646.77	2963.42
21	1685292.34	4617.24
22	2897723.62	7938.97
23	2199670.16	6026.49
24	332302.11	910.42
25	1061201.48	2907.4
26	69335.55	189.96
27	343222.61	940.34
28	287398.91	787.39
29	149501.41	409.59
30	355751.07	974.66
31	620573.97	1700.2

32	28622.98	78.42
33	31717.36	86.9
35	17990.41	49.29
36	177548.54	486.43
37	1413392.23	3872.31
38	491576.65	1346.79
39	262025.12	717.88
40	554986.32	1520.51
41	344899.06	944.93
42	176899.87	484.66
43	411445.52	1127.25
44	151401.15	414.8
Total	46577524.55	127609.68

Figure 4.12 Expected Daily Milk Consumption According to January Buildings.

Figure 4.13 Expected Yearly Milk Consumption According to January Buildings.

Maps analysis: Figure (4.12) and Figure (4.13) show the highest districts potential that required the planning team, and decision maker’s to focus in, the dark blue reflect the highest expected consumption while the medium yellow is the lowest potential market size (district with no colour mean there are no buildings at that time).

4.3.2. October Milk Market Size

4.3.2.1. Daily Milk Market Size Forecasting

This section discusses the methodology of forecasting the demand for drinking water according to the population growth studied, based on the increase in urban growth. As we reviewed, we have the population growth depending on the new buildings and its stages, which will give us the chance to calculate the population needs for different products like drinking water continuously. Will consider the expected needs after three months, six months, one year, two years and the cumulative needs for the same periods, will study it daily and yearly.

A. Daily Milk market size after three months

At the beginning of 2016 (at January) the expected population was 1160087 person, (table 9), so we calculated its expected Milk needs (127609.68 L per day), the planned capacity of the study area can increase by 62545 persons after three months, here we can know the expected human milk needs after this period by applying this equation:

$$DM = Ex\ POP (n) * AVE\ M \quad 4.1.$$

DM = Daily Milk needs

Ex POP (n) = expected population growth after (n) period, n = three month

AVE M = person's daily milk consumption

Daily Milk needs= population for this period * person's daily consumption (0.11 L)
=62545*0.11= 6879.95 L/ day.

This means we will need after three months (starting from April 2016) 6879.95 L Milk every day for those new people in studying area (Figure (24), here the concerned companies must planning to meet these requirements.

Figure 4.14 Daily Expected Milk Market Size (Three Month Later)

Then we can expect the cumulative market size for the same period (three months), we can calculate it with this equation:

$$\text{CUM DM (n)} = \text{DM (n)} + \text{DM (n-t)} \quad 4.2$$

CUM DM (n) = Cumulative milk market size a specific periods

DM (n-t) = previous period Market size

N = October

t = previous period (here January 2016)

Cumulative milk market size= Daily milk needs for this period + previous period Market size (here January) = 6879.95 + 127559.65 =127559.65 L per day, Figure (4.15)

Figure 4.15 Daily Cumulative Expected Milk Market Size (Three Month Later)

The consumption at the districts level shown in the following table (4.8), it showed the difference between expected cumulative consumption and expected to increase for the same period as a result of the increase in population in each district.

Table 4.8 Daily Expected Milk Market Size Three Months later

District	Three Month later (litre)	Three months cumulative (Litre)
1	66.24	5898.1
2	148.66	7874.55
3	146.54	6964.55
4	12.72	4940.93
5	33.91	2554.83
6	51.41	2128.38
7	42.39	1805.64
8	65.88	1674.98
9	42.14	2513.99
10	72.36	10028.28
11	22.52	5074.1
12	92.47	6310.83
13	143.51	4183.08
14	104.39	1001.65
15	412.1	7957.03
16	95.13	8877.07
17	114.74	6084.38
18	109.42	1038.56
19	63.34	1042.36
20	315.35	3278.77
21	173.05	4790.29
22	128	8066.97
23	349.75	6376.25
24	253.05	1163.47
25	451.29	3358.69
26	208.54	398.5
27	416	1346.53
28	21.19	808.59
29	2.12	411.71
30	70.48	1045.14
31	186.56	1886.76
32	2.12	80.54
33	36.03	122.93
35	10.6	59.89
36	20.41	506.84
37	189.96	4062.27
38	805.19	2131.39
39	173.79	891.67
40	566.82	2077.52
41	206.17	1151.1
42	85.07	569.73
43	261.21	1378.65
44	107.3	522.1
Grand Total	6879.93	134439.58

Figure 4.16 Difference Between Market Size and Cumulative Market Size After Three Months

Figure 4.16 explain how we can distinguish between the cumulative market size and the increasing market size for the same period. The cumulative size will tell us how much the market size will be after the period that we want to prepare to forecast to it, while the increase in market size tells us only what the expected value that added to the market, the cumulative demand is higher than the other value.

B. Daily Milk market size for the others periods

With the same methodology, Milk market size can expect for different periods. For Milk market size, the table (4.9) shows the market size for varying periods, while the table (4.10) shows us the expected cumulative milk market size for the same periods.

Table 4.9 Daily Expected Consumption According to October Buildings at Districts
Level (by Litre)

District	January	Three Month later	Six Month later	One Year later	Two Year later	Grand Total
1	5831.86	66.24	2.12	18.29	0	5918.51
2	7725.89	148.66	10.6	35.24	9.81	7930.19
3	6818.02	146.54	8.48	21.19	9.81	7004.03
4	4928.21	12.72	10.6	29.43	0	4980.95
5	2520.92	33.91	0	8.48	0	2563.31
6	2076.97	51.41	0	6.36	9.81	2144.54
7	1763.25	42.39	6.36	50.87	1.93	1864.79
8	1609.1	65.88	14.84	45.47	1.93	1737.22
9	2471.85	42.14	2.12	14.05	9.81	2539.97
10	9955.92	72.36	6.36	63.09	29.43	10127.15
11	5051.57	22.52	23.31	32.33	0	5129.74
12	6218.37	92.47	6.36	6.36	9.81	6333.36
13	4039.57	143.51	36.03	82.45	9.81	4311.37
14	897.25	104.39	6.36	61.22	9.81	1079.03
15	7544.93	412.1	33.91	104.15	29.43	8124.51
16	8781.94	95.13	10.6	14.05	9.81	8911.52
17	5969.64	114.74	12.72	20.41	9.81	6127.31
18	929.14	109.42	23.31	50.08	10.77	1122.73
19	979.03	63.34	4.24	69.69	0	1116.3
20	2963.42	315.35	42.39	175.17	49.04	3545.37
21	4617.24	173.05	48.75	61.76	9.81	4910.61
22	7938.97	128	14.84	28.88	0	8110.69
23	6026.49	349.75	38.15	128.54	58.85	6601.79
24	910.42	253.05	61.46	72.6	68.66	1366.19
25	2907.4	451.29	78.42	201.94	49.04	3688.09
26	189.96	208.54	36.03	68.91	58.85	562.29
27	930.53	416	101.73	207.75	68.66	1724.67
28	787.39	21.19	33.91	6.36	0	848.86
29	409.59	2.12	4.24	9.81	0	425.76
30	974.66	70.48	14.84	99.66	29.43	1189.07
31	1700.2	186.56	14.84	164.28	19.62	2085.49
32	78.42	2.12	4.24	42.39	0	127.17
33	86.9	36.03	25.43	59.34	0	207.7
35	49.29	10.6	12.72	22.52	0	95.13
36	486.43	20.41	12.72	6.36	0	525.91
37	3872.31	189.96	82.66	76.84	29.43	4251.19
38	1326.2	805.19	192.87	171.9	19.62	2515.77
39	717.88	173.79	46.63	61.46	0	999.76
40	1510.7	566.82	80.54	182.61	39.23	2379.91
41	944.93	206.17	33.91	104.69	19.62	1309.32
42	484.66	85.07	10.6	35.24	19.62	635.18
43	1117.44	261.21	91.14	118.74	89.24	1677.76
44	414.8	107.3	55.11	82.66	9.81	669.67
Grand Total	127559.7	6879.93	1356.44	2923.61	800.27	139519.9

Table (4.10) Daily Expected Cumulative Consumption According to October Buildings
(by Litre)

District	January	Three months cumulative	Six months cumulative	One year cumulative	Two year cumulative
1	5831.86	5898.1	5900.22	5918.51	5918.51
2	7725.89	7874.55	7885.14	7920.38	7930.19
3	6818.02	6964.55	6973.03	6994.23	7004.03
4	4928.21	4940.93	4951.52	4980.95	4980.95
5	2520.92	2554.83	2554.83	2563.31	2563.31
6	2076.97	2128.38	2128.38	2134.73	2144.54
7	1763.25	1805.64	1811.99	1862.86	1864.79
8	1609.1	1674.98	1689.81	1735.29	1737.22
9	2471.85	2513.99	2516.11	2530.16	2539.97
10	9955.92	10028.28	10034.64	10097.73	10127.15
11	5051.57	5074.1	5097.41	5129.74	5129.74
12	6218.37	6310.83	6317.19	6323.55	6333.36
13	4039.57	4183.08	4219.11	4301.56	4311.37
14	897.25	1001.65	1008.01	1069.22	1079.03
15	7544.93	7957.03	7990.94	8095.09	8124.51
16	8781.94	8877.07	8887.67	8901.72	8911.52
17	5969.64	6084.38	6097.1	6117.5	6127.31
18	929.14	1038.56	1061.87	1111.95	1122.73
19	979.03	1042.36	1046.6	1116.3	1116.3
20	2963.42	3278.77	3321.15	3496.33	3545.37
21	4617.24	4790.29	4839.04	4900.8	4910.61
22	7938.97	8066.97	8081.81	8110.69	8110.69
23	6026.49	6376.25	6414.4	6542.94	6601.79
24	910.42	1163.47	1224.93	1297.53	1366.19
25	2907.4	3358.69	3437.11	3639.04	3688.09
26	189.96	398.5	434.53	503.44	562.29
27	930.53	1346.53	1448.26	1656.01	1724.67
28	787.39	808.59	842.5	848.86	848.86
29	409.59	411.71	415.95	425.76	425.76
30	974.66	1045.14	1059.98	1159.64	1189.07
31	1700.2	1886.76	1901.6	2065.88	2085.49
32	78.42	80.54	84.78	127.17	127.17
33	86.9	122.93	148.36	207.7	207.7
35	49.29	59.89	72.6	95.13	95.13
36	486.43	506.84	519.56	525.91	525.91
37	3872.31	4062.27	4144.93	4221.77	4251.19
38	1326.2	2131.39	2324.26	2496.16	2515.77
39	717.88	891.67	938.3	999.76	999.76
40	1510.7	2077.52	2158.06	2340.68	2379.91
41	944.93	1151.1	1185.01	1289.7	1309.32
42	484.66	569.73	580.33	615.57	635.18
43	1117.44	1378.65	1469.79	1588.52	1677.76
44	414.8	522.1	577.21	659.86	669.67
Grand Total	127559.65	134439.58	135796.02	138719.62	139519.9

Figure 4.17 Contribution of Cumulative Daily Expected Milk Market Size over the Year

Figure (4.17) shows the contribution of population growth rates to the population's milk need according to time during the study period, two years after October 2016.

Figures 4. 18 Daily Expected Milk Market Size (Six Months Later).

Figures 4. 19 Daily Cumulative Expected Milk Market Size (Six Months Later).

Maps analysis: Figure (4.18 and 4.19) show the highest districts potential that required the planning team and decision maker’s to focus on, the dark blue reflect the highest expected consumption while the red is the lowest potential market size, (district with no colour mean there are no buildings at that time), by using this maps we can determine where the decision makers have to take the right action on time to prevent any bottleneck in the future.

4.3.2.2. Yearly Milk Market Size Forecasting.

Knowledge of the expected annual market size will enhance the planning process and gives the ability to meet the requirements in time for having the necessary resources. With same mechanism which we used in the previous section (Daily Milk market size forecasting) to calculate the results for the yearly expected demand, Table (4.11) shows us the annual expected milk market size for the October population growth at districts level, its useful to have good knowledge about the people Milk needs for the required periods according to populations growth.

Table 4.11 Yearly Milk Consumption According to October Buildings Satge

District	January milk Demand	Three Month later	Six Month later	One Year later	Two Year later	Grand Total
1	2128628.36	24179.16	773.59	6674.42	0	2160255.53
2	2819950.01	54259.14	3867.97	12863.17	3580.04	2894520.34
3	2488576.31	53485.55	3094.38	7735.94	3580.04	2556472.22
4	1798797.04	4641.56	3867.97	10740.13	0	1818046.71
5	920137.26	12377.51	0	3094.38	0	935609.15
6	758093.36	18764	0	2320.78	3580.04	782758.19
7	643585.49	15471.88	2320.78	18566.26	705.11	680649.52
8	587320.04	24046.05	5415.16	16598.03	705.11	634084.39
9	902225.04	15381.7	773.59	5127.23	3580.04	927087.61
10	3633911.7	26409.76	2320.78	23027.45	10740.13	3696409.82
11	1843823.65	8221.61	8509.54	11801.65	0	1872356.45
12	2269704.1	33750.22	2320.78	2320.78	3580.04	2311675.92
13	1474442.01	52381.1	13151.1	30093.98	3580.04	1573648.24
14	327497.54	38103.85	2320.78	22344.04	3580.04	393846.26
15	2753898.75	150417.3	12377.51	38013.67	10740.13	2965447.35
16	3205409.67	34721.55	3867.97	5127.23	3580.04	3252706.47
17	2178917.82	41881.64	4641.56	7448.01	3580.04	2236469.08
18	339135.67	39938.97	8509.54	18278.33	3932.6	409795.11
19	357345.52	23117.64	1547.19	25438.42	0	407448.77
20	1081646.77	115102.52	15471.88	63937.76	17900.22	1294059.16
21	1685292.34	63164.16	17792.67	22541.79	3580.04	1792370.99
22	2897723.62	46720.94	5415.16	10542.39	0	2960402.12
23	2199670.16	127660.4	13924.69	46918.69	21480.26	2409654.21
24	332302.11	92363	22434.23	26499.94	25060.31	498659.58
25	1061201.48	164720.1	28622.98	73706.55	17900.22	1346151.34
26	69335.55	76117.52	13151.1	25150.49	21480.26	205234.93
27	339642.57	151839.56	37132.52	75829.59	25060.31	629504.55
28	287398.91	7735.94	12377.51	2320.78	0	309833.14
29	149501.41	773.59	1547.19	3580.04	0	155402.24
30	355751.07	25726.35	5415.16	36376.29	10740.13	434009.01
31	620573.97	68093.65	5415.16	59962.23	7160.09	761205.11
32	28622.98	773.59	1547.19	15471.88	0	46415.65
33	31717.36	13151.1	9283.13	21660.64	0	75812.23
35	17990.41	3867.97	4641.56	8221.61	0	34721.55
36	177548.54	7448.01	4641.56	2320.78	0	191958.9
37	1413392.23	69335.55	30170.17	28047.13	10740.13	1551685.2
38	484064	293892.96	70397.07	62743.12	7160.09	918257.24
39	262025.12	63434.72	17019.07	22434.23	0	364913.14
40	551406.28	206889.67	29396.58	66654.02	14320.18	868666.72
41	344899.06	75253.74	12377.51	38211.41	7160.09	477901.8
42	176899.87	31051.32	3867.97	12863.17	7160.09	231842.42
43	407865.48	95341.63	33264.55	43338.64	32572.95	612383.25
44	151401.15	39165.37	20113.45	30170.17	3580.04	244430.19
Grand Total	46559271.76	2511173.58	495100.25	1067117.29	292098.9	50924761.77

Figure 4.20 Yearly Expected Milk Market Size (Three Month Later)

4.3.2.3. Cumulative Yearly Milk Market Size Forecasting

We will need to calculate the cumulative annual volume of milk to form a broader idea of the actual need for the population based on the consumption data that previously estimated in the daily tables.

Table (4.12) shows us the yearly cumulative expected milk market size for October growth at districts; this table provides us with the reading for the requirements to put it in our plan.

Table 4.12 Yearly Cumulative Consumption According to October Buildings (Litre)

District	January milk Demand	Three Month cumulative	Six Month cumulative	One Year cumulative	Two Year cumulative
1	2128628.36	2152807.52	2153581.11	2160255.53	2160255.53
2	2819950.01	2874209.15	2878077.12	2890940.3	2894520.34
3	2488576.31	2542061.86	2545156.24	2552892.18	2556472.22
4	1798797.04	1803438.6	1807306.57	1818046.71	1818046.71
5	920137.26	932514.77	932514.77	935609.15	935609.15
6	758093.36	776857.36	776857.36	779178.14	782758.19
7	643585.49	659057.37	661378.15	679944.41	680649.52
8	587320.04	611366.09	616781.24	633379.28	634084.39
9	902225.04	917606.74	918380.33	923507.56	927087.61
10	3633911.7	3660321.45	3662642.23	3685669.69	3696409.82
11	1843823.65	1852045.26	1860554.8	1872356.45	1872356.45
12	2269704.1	2303454.31	2305775.1	2308095.88	2311675.92
13	1474442.01	1526823.11	1539974.21	1570068.19	1573648.24
14	327497.54	365601.39	367922.18	390266.22	393846.26
15	2753898.75	2904316.05	2916693.55	2954707.22	2965447.35
16	3205409.67	3240131.22	3243999.19	3249126.43	3252706.47
17	2178917.82	2220799.46	2225441.02	2232889.03	2236469.08
18	339135.67	379074.64	387584.18	405862.51	409795.11
19	357345.52	380463.16	382010.35	407448.77	407448.77
20	1081646.77	1196749.3	1212221.18	1276158.94	1294059.16
21	1685292.34	1748456.5	1766249.17	1788790.95	1792370.99
22	2897723.62	2944444.57	2949859.73	2960402.12	2960402.12
23	2199670.16	2327330.56	2341255.26	2388173.94	2409654.21
24	332302.11	424665.1	447099.33	473599.28	498659.58
25	1061201.48	1225921.58	1254544.57	1328251.12	1346151.34
26	69335.55	145453.07	158604.17	183754.66	205234.93
27	339642.57	491482.13	528614.65	604444.24	629504.55
28	287398.91	295134.85	307512.36	309833.14	309833.14
29	149501.41	150275	151822.19	155402.24	155402.24
30	355751.07	381477.42	386892.58	423268.88	434009.01
31	620573.97	688667.63	694082.79	754045.02	761205.11
32	28622.98	29396.58	30943.77	46415.65	46415.65
33	31717.36	44868.46	54151.59	75812.23	75812.23
35	17990.41	21858.38	26499.94	34721.55	34721.55
36	177548.54	184996.55	189638.12	191958.9	191958.9
37	1413392.23	1482727.77	1512897.94	1540945.07	1551685.2
38	484064	777956.96	848354.03	911097.15	918257.24
39	262025.12	325459.83	342478.91	364913.14	364913.14
40	551406.28	758295.95	787692.53	854346.55	868666.72
41	344899.06	420152.8	432530.3	470741.71	477901.8
42	176899.87	207951.19	211819.16	224682.33	231842.42
43	407865.48	503207.11	536471.66	579810.3	612383.25
44	151401.15	190566.53	210679.98	240850.15	244430.19
Grand Total	46559271.76	49070445.33	49565545.58	50632662.87	50924761.77

Figure 4.21 Yearly Cumulative Expected Milk Market Size (Three Month Later)

Analysis:

In this section, population data that were estimated based on the type and quantity of existing residential buildings and the size and type of growth in the residential building sector were used to determine the approximate milk market size in various periods, depending on the speed of establishing suitable conditions for the occupancy of the new buildings. This prior knowledge will enable a broad and comprehensive understanding of strategic requirements Of the population to meet their needs of the required products.

4.4. Building Materials

The High-resolution satellite image has been used to extract the new buildings which built after the January 2016. The number of these opportunities was 4268 and classified according to the building type and its construction level as in Table (3.2). Based on the new division of the study area, in each micro-geographic area using a geographic information system (GIS) to determine growth in micro-geographic.

By identifying the number of new buildings and the type of each building in each micro-geographic, and using Table (3.2) which explain the average number of (switches and sockets) needed by each building type, then we can calculate the market size in the studying area, it is possible to know the needs of each micro-geographic area for the products and their distributions using geographic information systems. Figure (4.22) explain the market size at micro-geographic area level which using GIS to convert the data to visual map to know the potential market size for each district.

Building materials are a critical factor in human activity and urban development; Logistic operations are the cornerstone to provide the sites with these materials and keeping the sufficient stock to prevent any bottlenecks in the stock or to keep due to manufacturing excess quantities. To keep our resources, we have to forecast the market size for these materials by expecting when the activities to conduct on dates that are aware of the duration that we may need these materials. At this time, remote sensing provides new tools and readable data after analysing it; this information will give us about the expected time for products installation and how much we need. In the following, we will use satellite data for products forecasting and planning to study the switches and socket market size.

A survey conducted for this products to know the number of switches which each building needs during the finishing stage, groups that were targeted by this survey is the electricians and contractors at the sites, the question was:

- a) How many products each buildings type need?
- b) Time to install the product (finishing stage)!

Results tabulated in Table (3.2 &3.3)

Determine the current building construction stage is very important to estimate the periods that building needs to install this product, the construction building stages are:

- a) Basements
- b) Under construction
- c) Construction completes

Switches study targeted the building which began construction after January 2016 or in another meaning after the first images have taken, if we have the number of buildings for each building type then we can expect the products quantities that we need (table 4.13)

Table 4.13 Total Construction Requirement for the Switches

Buildings type	Switches Average	Time to installation (Month)			Number of Buildings	Products Quantities
		Basement	Under construction	construction completed		
villa	193.66	12	6	3	3627	702410.1
Apartment	771.37	24	12	6	429	330918.5
Esteraha	48.63	24	12	6	57	2771.8
Mosque	104.67	24	12	6	15	1570.0
tower	4188.44	24	12	6	5	20942.2
Gas station	93.22	12	6	3	8	745.8
School	425.56	24	12	6	9	3830.0
Mall	227.25	24	12	6	1	227.3
showroom	351.38	12	6	3	94	33029.7
Palace	425.56	24	12	6	18	7660.0
warehouse	30.00	9	6	3	2	60.0
Governmental	1677.10	24	12	6	3	5031.3
					Sum	1109197

At the moment, we have become familiar with the expected building requirements of the products which can install in these buildings, but this information will be more valuable in case determine the time to install it and demand at the districts level. By using Geospatial information, we studied that the new constructions distributed over the districts, and we have an idea about how many new constructions for each district, Table (4.14) show the expected switches and sockets market size at districts level. Identify the number and type of new buildings in each district will allow determining the expected need for the products required to these buildings based on previous surveys which carried out.

Table 4.14 Show the Expected Switches Market Demand

District	Market size	District	Market size
1	7543.0	23	52648.6
2	18570.9	24	41603.0
3	17702.1	25	71699.5
4	4795.8	26	34347.2
5	5901.7	27	71055.4
6	6502.8	28	5967.6
7	10378.8	29	2552.4
8	14015.5	30	18565.8
9	5599.8	31	34234.8
10	16505.8	32	4805.6
11	8278.5	33	11438.7
12	10608.9	35	4415.0
13	29885.2	36	5034.0
14	15860.6	37	34678.3
15	51531.6	38	104527.4
16	14027.0	39	25757.0
17	13533.4	40	75627.4
18	17651.6	41	52217.2
19	12570.6	42	13043.2
20	50430.7	43	48719.4
21	25789.3	44	23181.0
22	15394.8		
		Total	373078.2 (piece)

The knowledge of the distribution of new buildings depending on the building type according to the districts is so essential that it helps to plan and organize the logistics activities better, Table (4.15)

Table 4.15 The New Buildings Distribution Depending on the Construction Type

the new buildings distribution at districts level depending on the construction type														
District	Apartment	Compound	Esteraha	Gaz Station	Governmental	Mall	Mosque	Palace	School	Showroom	Tower	villa	wherehouse	Grand Total
1	3											27		30
2	7								1	1		64		73
3	6		1							4		60		71
4	3									1		11		15
5					1					1		20		22
6	3									2		18		23
7								2	1			47		50
8	1							4		3		54	1	63
9	5											9		14
10	14								2	5		16		37
11	3						1			4		23		31
12	2									1		45		48
13	5						1	9	1	6		101		123
14	6											58		64
15	31			2					2	4		130		169
16	5									8		38		51
17	7											42		49
18	3							1				77		81
19	6								1	1		37		45
20	28		1							2		145		176
21	15		1				1			2		69		88
22	8									2		44		54
23	23		1	1						8		165		198
24	16			1			1			5		141		164
25	34		2		2		1			3		211		253
26	17		7							6		97		127
27	24		1			1				6		259		291
28										1		29		30
29	1		3							3		3		10
30	13		1	1			1			1		41		58
31	14	1	12									117		144
32										1		23		24
33			1							1		57		59
35	1									1		17		19
36	1		3							4		14		22
37	6		1	1			3			1		151		163
38	20						2					459		481
39												133		133
40	39		3				4			4		225		275
41	19									1	5	84		109
42	8		4	1								34		47
43	30		14					2	1	1		120	1	169
44	2		1	1								111		115
Grand Total	429	1	57	8	3	1	15	18	9	94	5	3626	2	4268

Figure 4.22 Expected Market Size for Switches for The New Buildings

4.4.1. The Increase in Market Size According to Periods

Estimating the market size in the studying area and Taking into account the time to products can be installed is very useful if we can do it, remote sensing gives the ability to have it, if consider tables (4.13 and 4.15), the results are the products increasing depending on the building stage and time to install it, table (4.16). This is meaning: three months starting from October 2016 (approximately at January 2017) we will need 445604 new switches while after two years, 67173 new switches will need to install it and so on,

at this time we don't care for other buildings that Which can be built in the studying area but we can be taking into our account later.

Table 4.16 The Demand for New Products According to Building Stage and Building Type

District	Expected market size according to the period (piece)				Grand Total
	Three Month	Six Month	One Year	Two Year	
1	4260.55	1736.4	1546.02	0	7542.97
2	9102.09	4825.17	3446.69	1196.93	18570.87
3	9611.19	4631.5	2688	771.37	17702.06
4	1161.97	1319.69	2314.12	0	4795.77
5	3098.58	351.38	2451.75	0	5901.71
6	2904.92	1542.74	1283.74	771.37	6502.78
7	3873.23	580.98	4647.87	1276.67	10378.75
8	5386.58	2933.94	4843.83	851.11	14015.45
9	1161.97	2507.78	1158.69	771.37	5599.81
10	2130.28	5140.6	6495.25	2739.67	16505.8
11	1161.97	4307.17	2809.38	0	8278.52
12	7552.8	1352.36	932.36	771.37	10608.89
13	12989.26	5260.54	10863.99	771.37	29885.17
14	7746.46	2123.73	5219.04	771.37	15860.59
15	17393.59	21636.12	10187.77	2314.12	51531.59
16	6706.26	3282.42	3266.97	771.37	14027.03
17	6003.5	5018.83	1739.68	771.37	13533.38
18	9102.09	2901.65	4450.94	1196.93	17651.6
19	3098.58	3126.99	6345.06	0	12570.64
20	16618.94	15072.44	14882.47	3856.86	50430.71
21	7746.46	11445.19	5826.25	771.37	25789.27
22	5773.9	6755.23	2865.7	0	15394.84
23	25584.65	10359.64	12076.06	4628.23	52648.58
24	17644.53	11120.45	7438.42	5399.6	41603
25	25261.82	25272.99	17203.13	3961.53	71699.47
26	14987.19	8934.98	5796.75	4628.23	34347.15
27	30103.36	17760.85	17564.33	5626.85	71055.39
28	1936.61	3449.96	580.98	0	5967.56
29	545.04	387.32	1620.01	0	2552.38
30	4999.25	3096.26	8156.22	2314.12	18565.85
31	10460.26	7526.6	14705.17	1542.74	34234.78
32	193.66	387.32	4224.61	0	4805.59
33	3292.24	2323.94	5822.53	0	11438.71
35	1319.69	1161.97	1933.34	0	4415
36	1671.07	2636.1	726.87	0	5034.03
37	16603.07	8884.88	6876.27	2314.12	34678.34
38	63714.62	26317.61	12952.4	1542.74	104527.37
39	15880.24	4260.55	5616.18	0	25756.97
40	32585.01	25310.02	14542.21	3190.15	75627.39
41	9876.73	11163.68	29634.07	1542.74	52217.23
42	3385.47	4825.17	3289.82	1542.74	13043.19
43	11924.13	19746.71	9255.05	7793.46	48719.35
44	9050.28	5806.57	7552.8	771.37	23181.01
Grand Total	445604.09	308586.44	287832.8	67173.25	1109196.57

Figure 4.25 Increase in Switches and Sockets Six Months Later

Figure 4.26 Increase in Switches and Sockets one Year Later

Figure 4.27 Increase in Switches and Sockets Two Years Later

Maps analysis: Figure (4.24 to 4.27) show the highest expected market size over time, those districts required the planning team and decision maker's to focus on, the dark blue reflect the most upper expected switches and socket market size while the medium yellow is the lowest potential market size, (district with no colour mean there are no buildings at that time), by using this maps we can determine where they have to take the right action on time to prevent any bottleneck in the future.

4.4.2. Cumulative Market Size For Switches and Sockets

Knowing the amount of expected increase in market size will lead us to understand the cumulative increase that may occur in the market, which requires identifying the priorities and preparing the necessary plans for that.

It's essential to know that, so we will have a full idea of the expected total number that we will need according to previous dates, table (4.17), here will have information about The total quantities of new products we will need, example: after two years the cumulative products that the studying area will need is 1109196 new switches.

Table 4.17 Cumulative Market Size According to Building Stage and Building Type.

District	Expected cumulative market size according to the period (piece)			
	Three Month	Six Months cumulative	One year cumulative	Two year cumulative
1	4260.6	5997.0	7543.0	7543.0
2	9102.1	13927.3	17373.9	18570.9
3	9611.2	14242.7	16930.7	17702.1
4	1162.0	2481.7	4795.8	4795.8
5	3098.6	3450.0	5901.7	5901.7
6	2904.9	4447.7	5731.4	6502.8
7	3873.2	4454.2	9102.1	10378.8
8	5386.6	8320.5	13164.3	14015.5
9	1162.0	3669.8	4828.4	5599.8
10	2130.3	7270.9	13766.1	16505.8
11	1162.0	5469.1	8278.5	8278.5
12	7552.8	8905.2	9837.5	10608.9
13	12989.3	18249.8	29113.8	29885.2
14	7746.5	9870.2	15089.2	15860.6
15	17393.6	39029.7	49217.5	51531.6
16	6706.3	9988.7	13255.7	14027.0
17	6003.5	11022.3	12762.0	13533.4
18	9102.1	12003.7	16454.7	17651.6
19	3098.6	6225.6	12570.6	12570.6
20	16618.9	31691.4	46573.9	50430.7
21	7746.5	19191.6	25017.9	25789.3
22	5773.9	12529.1	15394.8	15394.8
23	25584.7	35944.3	48020.4	52648.6
24	17644.5	28765.0	36203.4	41603.0
25	25261.8	50534.8	67737.9	71699.5
26	14987.2	23922.2	29718.9	34347.2
27	30103.4	47864.2	65428.5	71055.4
28	1936.6	5386.6	5967.6	5967.6
29	545.0	932.4	2552.4	2552.4
30	4999.3	8095.5	16251.7	18565.9
31	10460.3	17986.9	32692.0	34234.8
32	193.7	581.0	4805.6	4805.6
33	3292.2	5616.2	11438.7	11438.7
35	1319.7	2481.7	4415.0	4415.0
36	1671.1	4307.2	5034.0	5034.0
37	16603.1	25488.0	32364.2	34678.3
38	63714.6	90032.2	102984.6	104527.4
39	15880.2	20140.8	25757.0	25757.0
40	32585.0	57895.0	72437.2	75627.4
41	9876.7	21040.4	50674.5	52217.2
42	3385.5	8210.6	11500.5	13043.2
43	11924.1	31670.9	40925.9	48719.4
44	9050.3	14856.9	22409.6	23181.0
Grand Total	445604.1	754190.5	1042023.3	1109196.6

Figure 4.28 The Increase in Market Size

Analysis: This chart shows that the highest cumulative market size happened two years later starting in October 2016 while the lowest cumulative market size three months later starting in October 2016.

Figure 4.29 Expected Cumulative Switches Market Size (Three Months Later)

Figure 4.30 Expected Cumulative Switches Market Size (Six Month Later)

Figure 4.31 Cumulative Switches Market Size (One Year Later)

Figure 4.32 Cumulative Switches Market Size (Two Years Later)

Maps analysis: Figure (4.29 to 4.32) show the highest expected cumulative market size over time to tell us the where the districts with the highest potential which is dark blue while the medium yellow is the lowest potential market size (District with no colour mean there are no buildings at that time), by using this maps we can determine where they have to take the right action on time to prevent any bottleneck in the future.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

5.1. Conclusion

Through working in the business, we found that many companies have spatial data such as the company's location, its branches; the distributor's sites, and customers. So we have seen that adding spatial information, will give us a better vision to determine where the better places for the activities, and the suitable market trends. What the better business operations, we saw how linking all this data with its geographic context in a way that gives a better picture of reality and that is provided by remote sensing technology with GIS.

We have also studied and developed a methodology based on high-resolution satellite images with geographic information systems to know the market size by analysing these images and identifying the buildings types, its Quantities. Those data were linked it with the spatial data to improve the market reading.

The market size studied for certain types of products which can extend it to many products, the accuracy of the expectations of the market size to increase the sales operations and planning operations through the analysis of the construction level and predict the time necessary for the consumption or installation of products.

5.2. Recommendation

This research is based on the manual digitizing for the boundaries and components of the study area, including new buildings or under construction buildings

It may take much time, the output preparation depends on equations and processes within the GIS sequence and logical but requires preparation for each.

We can improve this research by enhancing the automatic extraction of the new buildings and classify it to its building type and stage.

This improvement will allow the full usage for this new methodology and improve the visibility studies for the targeting products that we need to prepare to forecast and determine the market size for it.

Besides, it is possible to increase efficiency through the development of scripts within the GIS program, which includes tabs for study parameters. This development in the program will allow the user to obtain the results immediately and shorten all the operations that will be done by the user and also through the model builder under GIS to shorten some processes by incorporating them in the one environment.

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